

Reflective Report on Stellenbosch University SIAN Conference and Tour of the Main Library
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“How equitable are our partnerships? How do we ensure mobility opportunities are accessible to all students? Are we accountable for our projects? Do we show compassion in our engagement with international students? Do we ensure respect in our engagement with partners?”

Mr. Robert Kotzé, SU’s Senior Director
of Internationalization, Stellenbosch University

I recently had the privilege of attending the 2025 Stellenbosch International Academic Networks (SIAN) Conference at Stellenbosch University (SU) in South Africa. With insightful workshops on responsible internationalization, partnership frameworks, and digitally enhanced global learning, the event attracted hundreds of delegates from six continents, all coming together to discuss the conference’s central theme, “Responsible Internationalization,” in higher education. For Stellenbosch University, responsible internationalization means integrating an international, global, and intercultural dimension that is ethical and sustainable into all aspects of the university’s life in alignment with core institutional values.

On the afternoon of March 11, Mr. Robert Kotzé, SU’s senior director of internationalization, led a campus tour. We learned how the University has been actively working to address its racist past and foster a more inclusive, diverse, and equitable academic environment for the *Maties* (the nickname for SU students). Given its historical ties to apartheid-era policies and Afrikaner nationalism, the university has undertaken several initiatives to confront its legacy and promote transformation. SU launched the “Visual Redress Project” to address symbols, artwork, and historical representations on campus that reinforce a colonial and apartheid-era legacy that includes renaming buildings previously named after figures associated with racism and apartheid, replacing offensive artwork and statues with inclusive representations of diverse South African identities, and updating campus spaces to reflect the university’s commitment to inclusivity and transformation.

Historically, SU was an Afrikaans-dominated institution, which created barriers for non-Afrikaans speakers. In recent years, curriculum reform, including African perspectives, critical race studies, and multilingual language policies, have been integrated to prevent the exclusion of non-Afrikaans speakers.

In 2018, The university commissioned an independent inquiry into its historical role in supporting apartheid policies. The findings acknowledged that SU was complicit in apartheid ideologies and contributed to racial exclusion. This report formed the basis for further reconciliation efforts. In October 2022, the University formally apologized for its role in apartheid, acknowledging how its policies and academic research contributed to institutionalized racism. This public apology was a symbolic yet significant step in addressing past injustices. The university has established “The Equality Unit,” which handles cases of discrimination, promotes a culture of inclusion, and has hosted conferences and dialogues on race, reconciliation, and justice. Despite these initiatives, transformation efforts at SU remain a work in progress. Conservative groups have opposed these changes. I spoke with students of color who argue that the primarily symbolic changes have been too slow, and incidents of racial discrimination on campus have sparked debates about the university’s culture.

I attended the welcome reception and dinner at Die Stal, Coetzenburg Sports Grounds, that evening. Hosted by Mr. Robert Kotzé, SU’s Senior Director of Internationalization, the event offered an informal opportunity to network and discuss strategic, equitable partnerships. This “family meeting,” as Kotzé described it, has grown from a small get-together in 2003 to a major annual event fostering “collaboration, understanding, and shared growth.”

On March 12, I attended three structured panel discussions at the Wallenberg Research Centre at STIAS (Stellenbosch Institute for Advanced Study): **Responsible Internationalization – Global Trends; the Value of a Partnership;** and **Parallel Workshops on Best Practices and Innovation.** The conference was split into three concurrent sessions focusing on more specialized topics. I attended the workshop on integrating sustainability into internationalization practices, where we discussed how to incorporate sustainability thinking into everyday campus operations. My group came up with the idea to create a digital map that shows students how they can reduce waste and find resources like food pantries.

Stellenbosch University Library Systems

On 13 March, SU hosted a Study Abroad Fair at the Jan Mouton Learning Centre. Since UNCG did not have a booth, I spent the day visiting the main library touring the Maker Space and special collections. Stellenbosch University (SU) has an extensive library management system that supports its students, faculty, and researchers across various disciplines and several branch libraries that include the main library, the Matie Community Service Library (community engagement and outreach), the Music Library, Engineering and Forestry Library, the Medicine and Health Sciences Library, the Theology Library, and the Bellville Park Campus Library

SU offers a range of workshops to support students, researchers, and faculty in developing information literacy, research skills, and digital proficiency. I toured the main library, which offers electronic resources, research support, study spaces, special collections, and a Maker Space. SU libraries integrate cutting-edge technology. Instructional services include embedded subject librarians who provide reference support, one-on-one consultation,

collaboration with faculty to integrate library resources into coursework, and digital learning to support students and researchers. “SUNSearch” is an advanced library management system that allows users to find books, e-books, articles, and other materials. “SUNScholarData” promotes digitization and open-access research through its institutional repository.

MakerSpace

As an intersection where technology, design, and education converge, SU officially opened its Makerspace in 2021. Directed by Mr. Hebler, the MakerSpace offers a modern, creative hub designed to support innovation, creativity, and hands-on learning. The core objective of the Makerspace is to foster critical thinking, collaboration, and multidisciplinary learning while empowering users by giving them access to cutting-edge tools and technologies.

The facility offers various tools and equipment, including 3D printing, CAD software, laser cutting technology, virtual reality and augmented reality (VR/AR), and tools for working with electronics, including soldering irons, circuit boards, sensors, and components for assembling robotics projects. Useful for engineering, architecture, visual art, and scientific research.

The MakerSpace is designed to be inclusive and accessible, allowing a wide range of users—from students with no prior experience in these technologies to advanced users in specialized fields—to take advantage of the tools. It encourages collaboration and provides interdisciplinary learning opportunities among designers, engineers, artists, science and visual art students. In addition, it promotes a culture of problem-solving and entrepreneurship, such as the visual arts department’s use of soldering irons to make jewelry that is sold at retail. Several exhibits and display cases showcased how student coursework was fostered into physical prototypes or models.

The Carnegie Research Commons

A dedicated research environment primarily intended for master's and doctoral students, as well as researchers and academics, the Commons provides a quiet and supportive environment for postgraduate research endeavors. Established as a conducive space for focused research, it offers individual workstations, seminar rooms, and a relaxation area. Users are provided access to electronic resources, personalized assistance from skilled librarians, and support for research activities.

Special Collections

During my trip to Special Collections, I met with archivist Busi Mofu, who discussed the university’s collection of rare books, exhibition of Africana materials, manuscripts, and historical archives. We engaged in extensive dialog about how South African archives have reinforced or disrupted historical narratives. Scholar archivists Verne Harris and Achille Mbembe’s have written extensively about archival power. Postcolonial archives have worked to decolonize memory and reconfigure knowledge systems. Historically, archives have shaped narratives about race, colonialism, and apartheid and have been used as tools

of power during apartheid. Comparatively, we addressed how the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) and the Greensboro Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) have influenced archival practices in South Africa and Greensboro.

The decolonization of archives is essential for racial reconciliation and historical justice in South Africa. Colonial and apartheid-era record-keeping privileged state narratives while erasing Black voices. I intend to interview Mrs. Mofu to discuss her insight into how public history and memory are preserved, contested, and reclaimed in a post-colonial and post-apartheid society. By analyzing the intersections of trauma-informed archives, archival decolonization, digital tools, and community engagement, I seek to understand how the past is remembered, contested, and mobilized for contemporary racial justice. The findings will be summarized in an article contributing to South African and African American Studies by highlighting best practices in global archival justice, decolonizing research, reclaiming marginalized histories, and fostering more inclusive archival practices.